
PRACTICAL CLASSES AS A STRATEGY FOR TEACHING PHYSICS: AN EXPERIENCE REPORT

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15647907

Luara dos Santos Maracás¹

¹Environmental and Sustainability Engineering – Federal University of Southern Bahia
luaramaracas@hotmail.com
Lattes: <http://lattes.cnpq.br/8880104313323628>

Felipe Campos da Silva²

²Sanitary and Environmental Engineering – Federal University of Southern Bahia
Felipe.campos@gfe.ufsb.edu.br
Lattes: <http://lattes.cnpq.br/9313573215159411>

Murilo Pereira da Silva³

³Forestry Engineering – Federal University of Southern Bahia
mmpsmurilogta@gmail.com
Lattes: <http://lattes.cnpq.br/3534361270939302>

AT03: Teaching and Learning Methods and Practices

ABSTRACT: Physics is a challenging subject when taught through traditional lectures. The use of practical classes facilitates the understanding of the content, in addition to being stimulating. This technique, applied in engineering courses and related areas, is of fundamental importance for academic training. Thus, the present study aims to present the importance of experimental practical classes in the teaching of Physics and to report how the experience in the didactic laboratory contributes to the teaching-learning process in the engineering course. Eight Experimental Physics II activities were developed in the laboratory of the Federal University of Southern Bahia, Jorge Amado Campus, with weekly frequency. Four people per group were defined to carry out the experiments. The scripts, with content on waves, fluids and thermodynamics, were made available in SIGAA. At the end, the teacher requested the report of each practice. It was noticed, throughout the component, an increase in the interest of the students themselves in the practices, highlighting the importance of laboratory spaces. No limitations were observed. It is concluded that the classes were efficient for most students in the class, resulting in a positive and significant performance.

Keywords: Active learning; Teaching; Physics; Training; Experimental Practices.

1. INTRODUÇÃO

In Brazil, teaching Physics is still often perceived as abstract knowledge, far removed from students' reality. Along with Mathematics, these are subjects considered the most challenging in the high school curriculum (MARCIA and POLIANA, 2013). With traditional teaching methods, the role of training citizens prepared for professional life has proven to be

limiting for science education due to the tendency to base teaching on intense memorization of formulas and theoretical concepts, which hinders interest in the subject and, consequently, learning (COSTA et al., 2011).

Physics in Brazilian education is related to a relatively recent historical and evolutionary path; the first undergraduate course in physics was created in 1934 at the Faculty of Philosophy, Sciences and Letters of USP (ROSA, 2005). Since then, the subject has gained relevance, especially in courses such as Engineering. The study of natural phenomena contributes to the development of a humanistic view of science, which promotes the critical development of students and is essential for understanding the evolution of technological means and scientific knowledge. Furthermore, it is important for the training of engineers and other professionals in related areas (MOREIRA, 2000).

Given the importance of Physics in academic and professional training, studies on education have contributed to understanding the nature of the knowledge construction process and the way people learn. Thus, teachers must propose appropriate activities so that students understand the content and develop a greater interest in the subject (D'AVILA, 1999). In this sense, Physics education can be strengthened through experimental practices that allow the understanding and application of physical concepts to real problems.

The “experimental” method is described as an action that involves control and manipulation of variables, even at different levels. Its goal is to enable students to acquire skills and understand the connection between science and nature, in addition to expanding their experiences and developing the ability to interpret information and create deeper and more meaningful knowledge in the classroom (BARRIOS et al. 2011). This approach has been highlighted by teachers and students as effective, helping to reduce problems in learning and teaching physics in a consistent manner (ARAÚJO; ABIB, 2003).

Although they are certain about the importance of practical activities, teachers who use them extensively in their teaching practices know that conducting experiments is not the solution to everything in Physics teaching; students' learning presents limitations and doubts, making the problem worthy of being analyzed more carefully (VILLANI; CARVALHO, 1993).

Therefore, the availability of bibliographical works that discuss the pedagogical characteristics and didactic perspectives for Experimental Physics classes and their impacts on student education is scarce (SILVA et al., 2005). In view of this, this study aims to substantiate the importance of experimental practical classes in Physics teaching and report how the experience in the didactic laboratory influences education in the teaching-learning process in

the undergraduate engineering course.

2. METHODOLOGY

For the preparation of this work, eight practical sessions of Experimental Physics II were carried out during the first semester of 2025, in the laboratory of the Federal University of Southern Bahia, located at Ilhéus/Itabuna Highway - KM 22, Ilhéus BA, Jorge Amado Campus. Classes take place once a week.

For the development of the activities, in the first laboratory class, groups composed of a maximum of 4 students were defined. Then, the experiment scripts were made available in SIGAA (Integrated Academic Activities Management System), the manual was provided as an integral part, complementary to the experiments of the Experimental Physics II curricular component.

The practical and laboratory aspects related to the contents of waves, fluids and thermodynamics were addressed throughout the component through different experiments. The practical exercises carried out by the class, in order, were: Standing Longitudinal Wave; Standing Transverse Wave; Heat Propagation; Linear Expansion; Latent Heat and Specific Heat of Solids and Liquids.

The activities were planned so that the students had autonomy in the search for answers and solutions. The preparation of the reports included the treatment of the experimental data obtained, the construction of the graphs indicated in the script and the answers to the questions formulated in the question sheet, contributing to the development of technical and analytical skills. The submission of the reports prepared in groups must be done by only one member, with a maximum deadline of 15 days after the experimental class.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As the practical classes were held, a considerable increase in student interest was noted, especially in relation to handling equipment and setting up experiments. Thus, the active participation of students in the experiments reiterates the importance of direct contact between students and practice, helping to consolidate physical concepts previously seen as abstract.

The results observed confirm the observations of Wellington (1998), who highlights the benefits of laboratory activities in science teaching, which are often based on three types of arguments: cognitive, affective and associated with capabilities/skills.

In this way, this experience teaches students the limitations of applying physical theories

to real situations, and the many different ways to minimize experimental uncertainty, preparing students to deal with real situations in engineering, where precision and rigor are necessary. The purpose of this space is to demonstrate a basic physical principle, as well as to allow students to base the content covered in various areas of engineering, making practical learning qualifying for the understanding and efficient application of these concepts.

The standing longitudinal wave experiment focuses on studying the wave aspects of a spring, visualizing the nodes and bellies of a longitudinal wave, and obtaining harmonics in the spring. The standing transverse wave experiment aims at the same idea, both using the vibration generator as their main equipment.

The heat propagation experiment aims to study the mechanisms of thermal transmission, and the linear expansion experiment focuses on thermal conduction in solid materials. In the following classes, the linear expansion experiment was developed, which aims to study the forms of heat propagation through conduction in solid bodies.

In the latent heat of fusion experiment, the practice aims to study heat, more specifically, determining the latent heat of fusion of ice, and the isothermal transformation experiment aims to study the proportionality relationships between pressure and volume, more specifically, we seek to experimentally obtain the proportionality relationship between pressure and volume.

However, no limitations were observed, despite the limited time for performing experimental steps, the teacher was able to instruct on an individual and interactive level, especially in groups with greater initial difficulties. Nevertheless, the final investigated practices showed great pedagogical potential, providing students with a more tangible understanding of physical phenomena and linking theoretical content to real everyday life.

4. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to highlight the importance of practical classes in teaching Physics in engineering courses. Based on the activities carried out in the teaching laboratory of the Federal University of Southern Bahia, it was possible to observe a significant increase in the students' interest and performance throughout the course.

The practical classes brought students closer to the professional reality of engineering, which provided an integrated education. Going beyond abstract teaching, it facilitated the applied understanding of the content.

The experiments aimed at approaching topics such as waves, fluids and thermodynamics allow students to learn more contextually and vividly in relation to theoretical experience. The

active participation of students, through group work and report writing, helped to acquire academic and technical skills. Furthermore, no limitations were observed during the study, which confirms its feasibility and effectiveness. Therefore, it can be concluded that practical classes are crucial for the educational process of future engineers.

REFERENCES

- ARAÚJO, M. S.T.; ABID, M. L.V. S. - Atividades experimentais no ensino de Física: diferentes enfoques, diferentes finalidades. **Revista Brasileira de Ensino de Física**. vol.25. São Paulo (2003).
- BORGES, A. T. Novos rumos para o laboratório escolar de ciências. **Caderno Brasileiro de Ensino de Física**, v. 19, n. 3, p. 291-343, 2002.
- COSTA, E. M. A.; LOPES JÚNIOR, E. F.; LEMOS, A. H. C.; LOBO, A. M. Interesse e atitude dos estudantes de Administração e Ciências Contábeis em relação às disciplinas de formação básica. **Revista de Administração da UFSM**, Santa Maria, v. 4, n. 3, p. 433–450, 2011.
- D'ÁVILA, Ana Rita Lourenço Nogueira. **Utilização de materiais de baixo custo no ensino de Física**. Monografia, apresentada à Faculdade de Ciências da Universidade. São Paulo (1999).
- Guimarães, Ana Carolina F. G. - **Ensino de física usando recursos acessíveis - Colégio de Aplicação da Universidade Federal de Viçosa**. Trabalho de Conclusão de Iniciação Científica Jr. Viçosa, 2011.
- FRANCO, Yara. **Ensino de física com experimentos alternativos**. Colégio de Aplicação da Universidade Federal de Viçosa. Trabalho de Conclusão de Iniciação Científica Jr. Viçosa, 2009.
- GRANDINI, N. A.; GRANDINI, C. R. Os objetivos do laboratório didático na visão dos alunos do curso de licenciatura em física da UNESP-Bauru. **Revista Brasileira de Ensino de Física**, v. 26, n. 3, p. 251-256, 2004.
- MARCIA REGINA E POLONIA FUSINATO - Aplicações das Leis de Newton em nosso Cotidiano. Cadernos PDE Versão On-line ISBN - **Os desafios da escola pública paranaense na perspectiva do professor PDE**. vol. 1, (2013).
- PEREIRA, A. C.; PINHEIRO, A. R. C. Uma didática experimental no processo de ensino e aprendizagem de cinemática no 1º ano do Ensino Médio. **Revista REAMEC**, v. 8, n. 2, p. 272-289, 2020.
- ROSA, C. W., ROSA, A. B. Ensino de Física: objetivos e imposições no ensino médio, **Revista Electrónica de Enseñanza de las Ciencias** vol. 4, (2005).

SARAIVA-NEVES, M.; CABALLERO. C.; MOREIRA, M. A. Repensando o papel do trabalho experimental, na aprendizagem da física em sala de aula - um estudo exploratório. **Investigações em Ensino de Ciências**, v. 11, n. 3, p. 383-401, 2006.

SILVA, J. R. N.; SANTOS, A. L.; SILVA, G. A.; DAHORA, S. A. B. Construções conjuntas de práticas pedagógicas sobre ensino de física experimental entre docentes do ensino superior: análise do potencial de um grupo de planejamento conjunto. **Revista Brasileira de Ensino de Ciências**, v. 30, n. 1, p. 336-368, 2025.

SOUZA, D. M. **Atividade experimental no ensino de física: uma ferramenta didática na aprendizagem de conceitos físicos**. 2018.

WELLINGTON, J. Practical work in science: Times for a reappraisal. In Wellington, J (Ed.). *Practical work in school science: Which way now?*. Londres: Routledge, 3-15. *Which Way Now?* London: Routledge, 1998.

VILLANI, A.; CARVALHO, L. O. Representações mentais e experimentos qualitativos. **Revista Brasileira de Ensino de Física**, v. 15, n. 1 a 4, p. 74-89, 1993.